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Research Article

**A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY ON THE COMPLICATIONS OF
KALA PATHAR POISONING**¹Jawad-Ul-Hassan, ²Usama Bin Hassaan, ³M. Talha Afzal¹Aziz Fatima Medical and Dental College Faisalabad.

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Abstract:**Objective:** The aim of this study was to determine the complications of kala pathar poisoning.**Material and Methods;** The design of this study was a cross sectional study. This study was carried out at Aziz Fatima hospital Faisalabad and the duration of this study was from May 2020 to November 2020. In this study the suspected cases of kala pathar poisoning by history from the patients and the attendants of either gender and age more than 18 years were included. The cases with pre-existing renal, hepatic or cardiac failure were excluded. These cases were then assessed clinically in detail and with laboratory investigation like liver function tests, renal functions test, Electrocardiogram, serum electrolytes etc. were done to label particular complication.**Results:** In this study 100 cases of suspected kala pathar poisoning were included, out of which 70 (70%) were females and 30 (30%) males as in table 01. Out of 100, 92 (92%) presented with oral ingestion. The mean age was 25.34 ± 6.12 years. Pain in throat was the most common complication seen in 78 (78%) of cases. Hyperkalemia was the 2nd most common complication seen in 54 (54%) of cases followed by rhabdomyolysis seen in 20 (20%) of cases. Renal failure was seen in 18 (18%) and arrhythmias in 10 (10%) cases.**Conclusion:** Kala pathar is a fatal suicidal agent and pain in throat followed by hyperkalemia are the most reported complications.**Keywords:** Poisoning, Predisposing, Benzodiazepine, Kala Pathar, Hyperkalemia, Rhabdomyolysis**Corresponding author:****Jawad-Ul-Hassan,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Suicide is an important social as well as health issue in this developed era and its number is increasing in the recent past and it has almost doubled in the half of century in the Asian countries. There are multiple social, psychological and socio-economic factors predisposing for this unwanted act. Suicide can be done by harming own self by many ways. Ingestion of toxic substances is the most widely employed method. Sedative drugs i.e. benzodiazepine are the leading cause in under developed countries due to easily availability and paracetamol in the developed ones due to drug regulation acts. Kala pathar (Paraphenylene Diamine also known as PPPD), is a hair dyeing agent. It is cheap, easily available and its incidence for suicidal intention is increasing. PPD when mixed with water, metabolizes by cytochrome p 450 by oxidation and converts it into a very toxic product that can be extremely fatal.

Kala pathar poisoning can lead to various signs and symptoms; few of which are subtle and the others are fatal. These include pain in throat, vomiting, arrhythmias, rhabdomyolysis, hyperkalemia, renal failure, anaphylactic reactions etc. There are different case reports with percutaneous absorption but the toxicity is usually seen in oral ingestion and data has revealed that the maximum toxicity is seen after the six hours of intoxication. There is no specific antidote for PPD.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

In this study the suspected cases of kala pathar poisoning by history from the patients and the attendants of either gender and age more than 18 years were included. The cases with pre-existing renal, hepatic or cardiac failure were excluded. These cases were then assessed clinically in detail and with laboratory investigation like liver function tests, renal functions test, Electrocardiogram, serum electrolytes etc. were done to label particular complication. The data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS version 23. Categorical data was presented as frequency and percentage while numerical data as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

In this study 100 cases of suspected kala pathar poisoning were included, out of which 70 (70%) were females and 30 (30%) males as in table 01. Out of 100, 92 (92%) presented with oral ingestion as shown in table 1. The mean age was 25.34 ± 6.12 years (table 2). Pain in throat was the most common complication seen in 78 (78%) of cases. Hyperkalemia was the 2nd most common complication seen in 54 (54%) of cases followed by rhabdomyolysis seen in 20 (20%) of cases. Renal failure was seen in 18 (18%) and arrhythmias in 10 (10%) cases as displayed in table 03.

Table 1. Demographics

Variables		N	%
Gender	Male	30	30%
	Female	70	70%
Mode of toxicity	Oral	92	92%
	Trans dermal	08	8%

Table 2. Study variables

	Mean	Range
Age	25.34 ± 6.12	18-52 years
Weight	46.11 ± 9.34	24-85 kg
Duration of poisoning (hr)	8.12 ± 2.34	1-48 hours

Table 3. Complications

Complications	Number	Percentages
Pain in throat	78	78%
Hyperkalemia	54	54%
Rhabdomyolysis	20	20%
Renal failure	18	18%
Arrhythmia	10	10%
Acute hepatitis	8	8%

DISCUSSION:

Kala pathar is an easily available and cheap substance used for hair dye. It is recently being used for suicidal attempts and the data has shown a very high number of mortality and also wide range of complications almost involving any organ of the body leading to a high degree of morbidity in such cases even if survived. In this study out of 100 cases 70 (70%) were females against 30 (30%) males. The majority of the cases were young and were less than 30 years of age. These findings were also similar to the previous studies where it was seen that females are most reported cases and this can be explained by the fact that this is the most vulnerable age and due to various social and psychological factors these are more prone to commit suicide. In the present study 92 (92%) cases had oral intoxication as compared to only 8 (8%) cases with trans dermal absorption. Nirmla et al and Khan et al also revealed that around 90-95% of the cases presented with oral intake, that also supports the data that it is widely used as suicidal intent. Pain in the throat was the most revealed complication observed in the present study seen in 78 (78%) of the cases. Khuhro et al, in their short study carried on 16 cases, revealed that this complication was seen in all sixteen cases. They included all the cases with oral intake as compared to our where we had 92 cases of oral intake and 8 trans dermal absorption.

Hyperkalemia and rhabdomyolysis were the other two common complications and share the same pathophysiologic mechanism as the muscle breakdown predispose to more spillage of potassium and lead to hyperkalemia. Prabhakaran AC and Kellel H et al also had similar percentages and hyperkalemia in their study was seen in almost 50% of the cases. renal failure and arrhythmias were other uncommon complications and were also reported in lesser number of cases in the previous studies as well.

CONCLUSION:

Kala pathar is a fatal suicidal agent and pain in throat followed by hyperkalemia are the most reported complications.

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